

Substituted 1-Arylaminomethyl-5,6-dimethylbenzimidazoles and Related Products.

RAJENDRA S. VARMA

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow 226007

Manuscript received 30 October 1976, accepted 27 April 1977

A series of 1-arylaminomethyl-5, 6-dimethylbenzimidazoles (IV) and other derivatives have been synthesised from 5, 6-dimethyl-benzimidazole.

It has been observed that cyanocobalamin and folic acid are essential for the growth of certain micro-organisms. The presence of 5, 6-dimethylbenzimidazole nucleus in the structure of vitamin B₁₂ has led to the synthesis of several benzimidazole derivatives such as 5-methyl; 4,5-dimethyl and 2,5-dimethyl benzimidazoles as antagonists of this vitamin¹. In view of these observations it was considered of interest to design a number of compounds (I, II, III and IV) derived from 5,6-dimethylbenzimidazole as antagonists of B₁₂. Certain compounds (IV) described in this article may also be regarded as antagonists of folic acid because

they incorporate $-\text{CH}_2\text{NH}-$ $-\text{C}-\text{R}$ group

present in folic acid.

I, R = OH

II, R = $-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{Me}$

III, R = $-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-$ $-\text{NO}_2$

IV, R = $-\text{NH}-$

1-Hydroxymethyl-5, 6-dimethylbenzimidazole (I) was obtained by the treatment of formaldehyde with 5,6-dimethylbenzimidazole. Acetylation of I with acetic anhydride furnished II. When I was allowed to react with 4-nitrobenzoyl chloride there was obtained III. Various 1-arylaminomethyl-5,6-dimethylbenzimidazoles (IV) were prepared by two methods. In one procedure, 5,6-dimethylbenzimidazole, aqueous formaldehyde and an appropriate primary amine were condensed to yield IV. Direct condensation of I with amines comprised the other method. When a compound was prepared by employing both the procedures its identity was always checked by the comparison of m.p., m.m.p. and i.r. spectra.

I, II, III and IV thus synthesised were characterised by their satisfactory elemental analyses. Additional evidence was derived from their i.r. and n.m.r. spectral data. Characteristic i.r. bands were present in the spectra of I, II, III and IV (1,7,8,11,12; Table 1). The n.m.r. spectrum of 10 was in accord with the assigned structure. Two sharp singlets at δ 2.33 and 3.73 have been attributed to two methyl and one methoxyl protons, respectively. The signal due to CH₂ and NH observed at δ 5.36 as a broad band integrated for three protons. After D₂O exchange the integration of this signal indicated only two protons. Absorptions due to aromatic protons occurred at δ 6.66 (four protons at 3',4',5',6'), 7.16 (2-H) and 7.4-7.9 (two protons at 4 and 7 positions).

TABLE 1—1-ARYLAMINOMETHYL-5,6-DIMETHYLBENZIMIDAZOLES(IV)

Compound ^a	R'	M.P. °C.	Yield%
1. ^b	H	176	65
2.	2-Me	166-167	69
3-	3-Me	187-188	70
4.	4-Me	185	60
5.	4-OMe	176	60
6.	4-Cl	163-164	65
7. ^c	4-Br	160	70
8. ^d	3-Cl	187	60
9.	2-Cl	152	70
10. ^e	2-OMe	169-170	75
11. ^e	4-CO ₂ Me	160-161	65
12. ^f	4-CO ₂ Et	150-152	45
13.	4-F	157-158	55
14.	4-Ph	178	60
15.	4-CO ₂ H	207-208	65

^a. Satisfactory nitrogen analyses were obtained for all the compounds.

I.R. (μ): ^b. 3.10 (NH); ^c. 3.10 (NH); ^d. 3.12 (NH); ^e. 3.15 (NH), 5.85 (C=O); ^f. 2.99 (NH), 5.81 (C=O).

N.M.R. (δ): ^a. 2.33 (2 Me), 3.73 (OMe), 5.36 (-CH₂- and NH), 6.66 (Ar-H at 3', 4', 5', 6'), 7.16 (2-H), 7.4-7.9 (two protons at 4 and 7).

Compounds 1, 12, 15 were prepared by method B, others by method A.

All the compounds were screened for their inhibitory effect against four organisms: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Bacillus megaterium* by agar diffusion technique². Compounds 2 and 13 showed moderate inhibition against *B. megaterium*. 1 and 9 were active against *E. coli*. Other compounds were devoid of any activity.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 Spectrophotometer in KBr. N.M.R. spectrum was recorded on a Varian A-60-D Spectrometer in $CDCl_3$ using TMS as an internal standard.

1-Hydroxymethyl-5,6-dimethylbenzimidazole (I) — 5,6-Dimethylbenzimidazole (2.19 g.) was suspended in 25 ml of boiling water. Formalin (2 ml) was added to it in small portions with stirring. The reaction mixture after being stirred for 15 min. was left overnight. The solid product thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol, yield 75%; m.p. 137-138°; m. m. p. with 5,6-dimethylbenzimidazole 170-190°; i.r.: 3.25 μ (Found: N, 15.83%. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{12}N_2O$; N, 15.90%).

1-Acetoxyethyl-5,6-dimethylbenzimidazole (II) — I (1.0g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) were heated under reflux for 30 min. The contents were poured in 100 ml of cold water with stirring. The solid mass was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol; yield 65%; m.p. 225°; i.r.: 6.00 μ (C=O); (Found: N, 12.92%. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{14}N_2O_2$; N, 12.83%).

1-(4-Nitrobenzoyloxymethyl)-5,6-dimethylbenzimidazole (III) — Freshly prepared 4-nitrobenzoyl chloride (1.0 g.) dissolved in 25 ml of dry benzene was treated with 0.80 g. of I. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hr under anhydrous conditions. After

removing benzene by distillation the solid mass was triturated with 10% sodium carbonate solution. It was then washed with water and recrystallised (ethanol); yield 60%; m. p. 176°; i. r.: 5.78 μ (C=O), 6.49, 7.41 μ (NO₂) (Found N, 12.46. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{16}N_3O_4$; N, 12.91%).

1-Arylaminoethyl-5,6-dimethylbenzimidazole (IV) — Method A: To a hot solution of 5,6-dimethylbenzimidazole (1.46 g.; 0.01 mole) in 15 ml of ethanol, 1.5 ml of formalin and an appropriate amine (0.01 mole) were added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min. and then allowed to stand at room temp. overnight. The crude IV thus obtained was purified to analytical purity from ethanol.

Method B: A suitable aromatic amine (0.01 mole) and I (1.76 g.; 0.01 mole) were heated in 15 ml of ethanol for 30 min. After cooling the product was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. Various IV thus synthesised are listed in Table I along with their physical data.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks the Head of the Chemistry Department, Lucknow University for providing Laboratory facilities. Thanks are also due to Dr. R. S. Kapil and Dr. S. A. Imam for analytical and biological data. The gift of 5,6-dimethylbenzimidazole from K. Methaqualone and Chemicals, Lucknow is gratefully acknowledged. This work was supported in part from a U. P. SCST contingent grant.

References

1. A. BURGER, Medicinal Chemistry, 2nd Edition, Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, N. Y., 1960, p. 109.
2. R. S. VARMA and W. L. NOBLES, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1968, 57, 1801.